

Comparative life cycle assessment for evaluation of sludge management alternatives in developing countries

Dj. Kerkez, M Bečelić-Tomin, V. Pešić, D. Krčmar, D. Tomašević Pilipović, A. Leovac Maćerak

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Trg Dositeja Obradovica 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia; djurdja.kerkez@dh.uns.ac.rs, milena-becelic-tomin@dh.uns.ac.rs, vesna.pesic@dh.uns.ac.rs, dejan.krcmar@dh.uns.ac.rs, dragana.tomasevic@dh.uns.ac.rs, anita.leovac@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract: Wastewater treatment has nowadays multiple functions and produces both clean effluents and sludge, which is increasingly seen as a resource especially for nutrient recuperation. Developing countries face the urgent need to set out priorities and access different options in sludge management, while scarce relevant national databases at the same time. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) can determine what alternatives provide the best environmental performance in site-specific context. System border expansion is needed to envelop different end-of-life scenarios for sludge, and more comprehensive predictions. In developing countries, with introducing LCA as a possible decision making tool in sludge management options, it is necessary to include circular economy aspects such as the benefits of nutrient recuperation and saving and biogas recovery. In addition, building the national LC inventory is essential for more accurate and sound assessment for future wastewater treatment plants.

Keywords: sludge management; circular economy; life cycle assessment

In developing countries, wastewater treatment has improved in recent years but remains a high priority sustainability challenge. To achieve the United Nations (UN) sustainable development goal 6 “CleanWater and Sanitation” by 2030, a considerable effort in the construction and operation of wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) should be applied in these regions in the following years. In order to select the technology that should be applied in each case, compliance with stipulated environmental regulatory standards and technology costs should be considered alongside other aspects like geographic location, socioeconomic conditions or regional and global environmental impacts.

One of the instruments that can enable decision making in wastewater sector is life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology. LCA, now standardized, is often used in developed countries for evaluation of environmental impacts of products and services, considering a set of energy and material inputs and outputs throughout their life cycle, allowing the quantification of the effects of the entire system under study (e.g. climate change and resource depletion potentials), and not only aspects related to the facility surroundings. On the other hand, LCA is very rarely considered during the design and evaluation of WWTs in developing countries although it enables better decision making due to inclusion of more variables. In most studies LCA goal and system boundaries are clearly defined, but significant stages for some technologies such as sludge management are frequently not included although it may represent a significant contribution to overall impacts.

Today in the Republic of Serbia wastewater sector is not on satisfactory level. Only 10 % of necessary WWTP is built. Thorough different financial programs 359 units is planned to be constructed. With the future WWTP construction, the challenge of sludge disposal is evident. According to the Specific Implementation Plan of Directive 91/271/EC and Sludge management program in the Republic of Serbia for the period 2023-2032 the predicted maximal amount of sludge is slightly over 135 000 t DM/year. Currently, predominant disposal method for sludge is landfilling.

Although the Program emphasizes as a general goal "the establishment of a safe, sustainable and cost-effective sludge management system from wastewater treatment plants in accordance with the principles of the circular economy (CE)", the document does not recognize sludge as a resource, which would support the commitment to CE. The program mainly suggest mono-incineration for creating future phosphorus rich deposits. However, the program does not recognise hierarchy in sludge management option nor regional needs for this resource.

This study examines the possibility of using LCA to assess different sludge management options, and all challenges, gaps and conclusions that may arise from selecting goals, building specific data inventory and LCA development. One of the focus is to examine the LCA potential, as decision-making tool to be used for wastewater stakeholders in developing countries is to improve data quality in the first place and to use this method for future WWTPs.

Figure 1. Sludge management alternatives for LCA (1. Current practice, 2. Conventional (cost-effective) practice in accordance with regional needs, 3. Practice suggested by national sludge programme)

For the study the real WWTP was selected with 150 000 PE nominal capacity, that operates with Carrousel 2000 technology, and discharges its treated wastewater into waterbody sensitive for eutrophication, so more strict limits to phosphorus are applied. The sludge management is currently not sustainable and majority is landfilled

with only small share handled by co-composting. With turning to CE other sludge management options must be considered especially as sludge is of good quality (Figure 1). The LCA is focused on phosphorus recuperation as this resource is recognized as one of the priorities according to national sludge programme. The study emphasized the necessity for more site-specific databases. Eutrophication and global warming are the two most commonly assessed impacts. However, as all three scenarios include a form of land application the terrestrial ecotoxicity as one of the major impact should be encouraged. The final emission of heavy metals to the soil depend on the sludge quality and is site-dependent. Data on previous condition of the agricultural soil, where the sludge is to be applied, need to be considered as well. When including the agricultural application it is necessary to expand the system boundaries to include the positive effects of the nutrient value of the sludge by considering the substitution of chemical fertilizers. Impact categories with highest variability are those that are largely influenced by effluent and sludge quality, such as eutrophication and toxicity-related ones.

The LCA approach should be associated with plans and actions to face the challenges of providing wastewater treatment in developing countries. Furthermore, by including CE principles into the assessment, compliance with both environmental targets and public health protection can be achieved.

REFERENCES

- Bečelić-Tomin, M. & Kerkez, Dj. 2022 *Wastewater in the context of social challenges*. Faculty of Sciences, UNS, Novi Sad.
- Ding, A., Zhang, R., Ngo, H.H., He, X., Ma, J., Nan, J., & Li, G. 2021 Life cycle assessment of sewage sludge treatment and disposal based on nutrient and energy recovery: A review. *Sci. Total Environ.* **769**, 144451.
- Gallego-Schmid, A. & Tarpani, R.R.Z. 2019 Life cycle assessment of wastewater treatment in developing countries: A review. *Water Res.* **153**, 63-79.
- Lopes, T.A.S., Queiroz, L.M., Torres, E.A. & Kiperstok, A. 2020 Low complexity wastewater treatment process in developing countries: A LCA approach to evaluate environmental gains. *Sci. Total Environ.* **720**, 137593.
- Niero, M., Pizzol, M., Bruun, H.G. & Thomsen, M. 2014 Comparative life cycle assessment of wastewater treatment in Denmark including sensitivity and uncertainty analysis. *J. Clean. Prod.* **68**, 25-35.
- Nyitrai, J., Almansa, X.F., Zhu, K., Banerjee, S., Hawkins, T.R., Urgun-Demirtas, M., Raskin, L. & Skerlos, S.J. 2023 Environmental life cycle assessment of treatment and management strategies for food waste and sewage sludge. *Water Res.* **240**, 120078.
- Rashid, S.S., Harun, S.N., Hanafiah, M.M., Razman, K.K., Liu, Y.Q., & Tholibon, D.A. 2023 Life Cycle Assessment and Its Application in Wastewater Treatment: A Brief Overview. *Processes* **11**, 208.

19th IWA Leading Edge Conference on Water and Wastewater Technologies

ESSEN, GERMANY | 24-28 June 2024 | www.iwa-let.org

Sludge management program in the Republic of Serbia for the period 2023-2032.
year. 2023 "Official Gazette of RS", 30/18.

Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, Horizon Europe - Work Programme 2021-2022 Widening participation and strengthening the European Research Area, HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02*, under grant agreement No [101060110], SmartWaterTwin